

INNOVATIONS AS A FACTOR OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6353775>

Mamadaliyev Kodirjon Kobulzhonovich

Marketing Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies, Faculty of Agribusiness and Digital Economy, Associate Professor of the Department of Agribusiness and

Tojiddinov Sardorbek

Student, Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agrotechnologies

Annotation: *The article develops recommendations on the nature of innovation, the need for entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector and its impact on the development of the industry, the further development of innovation in the agricultural sector.*

Key words: *Innovation, innovative activity, innovative environment, transfer, cluster, modernization, diversification, globalization, agrifirm, farm.*

In the context of globalization knowledge, technologies, innovations form the leading force of the development of agricultural sector, ownership of which provides leadership in the continent, creates superiority in the competitiveness of agricultural products in international markets, has a positive impact on agricultural workforce productivity, increases the income of farms and agrifirms and most importantly, improves life standard of population in rural areas.

During the transition from an industrialized economy to an innovative economy sources of manufacturing and economic growth will change. In economy a country's economic growth is reached by investing the financial capital of formed countries and enterprises in financing technologies and innovations. Such innovations can be reflected on organizing labor and provision of high-qualified staffs.

In the table below foreigner scientists' views are given who explained the meaning of innovations and their impact on economy in their scientific work. The scientific nature of innovation began to be investigated after the 1920s in which an Australian scientist J. Schumpeter's views played an important role.

Scientific approaches about the need for innovations in economy

Author	Theory
J. Schumpeter ¹	Innovation is a leading factor in the development of socio-economic systems, the initiator of the innovation process is an entrepreneur, and innovation is a key factor in determining economic growth as a stage of cyclical development in the medium and long term.

¹ Schumpeter J. A. Business Cycles: a Theoretical, Historical, and Statistical Analysis of the Capitalist Process / J. A. Schumpeter. – Oxford Univ. Press, 1939. – 384 pages.

F. A. Hayek ²	Innovative activity and innovative development are relatively flexible to economic regulatory measurements: the less state control, the higher establishment of innovation in enterprises it means. Correspondingly, the development of structural conditions, stimulation of competition, removal of restrictions on entrepreneurial initiative are prerequisite for the development of socio-economic systems.
H. Chesbrough ³	The efficiency of innovative process is related to external, international scientific and technologic partnership activity, it results in a strong effect on the all counterparties of the real sector.

Innovations have a direct impact on agrarian and other sectors of economy as well as as real and other sector activities. Innovative development of agricultural system of a country depends on the internal effect of innovation and inflow of foreign investment activity.

Innovation plays an important role in the interaction of socio-economic systems with the economic links of the agricultural sector horizontally (at the same level) and vertically with subsystems (at the lower regional level). Regardless of the field of application of innovative activities, the presence of innovative interactions is able to achieve efficiency and stimulate other socio-economic systems. If innovations in the agricultural sector becomes more permanent and widespread, innovation activity will also expand in the infrastructure serving this sector. Foreign researches confirm that an innovative economy ensures the competitiveness and leadership of the economic system, including global economic development.

Dynamic changes in GDPs of the expenditures of countries on science

Countries	Years			
Countries	2012	2014	2016	2018
USA	2.7	2.73	2.72	2.74
China	1.9	2.0	2.1	2.3
Japan	3.2	3.1	3.2	3.1
S. Korea	4.0	4.3	4.2	4.2
Russia	1.0	1.1	1.1	1.2
Kazakhsta n	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.3
Uzbekista	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.18

² Хайек, Ф. А. Пагубная самонадеянность. Ошибки социализма / Ф. А. Хайек. – М., 1992. – 304 с. 4 Mensch, G. Stalemate in Technology: Innovations Overcome the Depression / G. Mensch. — New York, 1979. – 241 pages.

³ Chesbrough, H. Open Innovation. The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting from Technology / H. Chesbrough. – 2003.

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From the data in Table 2 above, we see the share of the countries' expenditures on science and innovation in GDP. Significant investments are being made in innovation in the world's leading countries. In the next 10 years, the investments of innovation tend to increase significantly. In developed countries, private sectors also invest heavily in innovation. Innovative development of the agricultural sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan provides not only the growth of innovation, production intensity, economic efficiency of agricultural enterprises in the regions, but also the whole cycle of innovation in agriculture in the country, including development, commercialization, real sector segments. It aims to create conditions to spread of innovations, as well as the expansion of intersectoral and interregional ties. Analyzing the innovative factors that develop agrarian sector includes:

- 1) Seeking the most effective ways of utilizing domestic opportunities that are factors of agricultural development and enhancing its expansion;
- 2) Developing the agrarian sector introducing foreign innovative methods. Innovation transfer is effectively used here.

Innovation transfer is an important part of innovation processes, is disseminating prescribed innovations to socio- economic sectors in particular, to business beneficently. The functionality of the approach in the study of systems for the application of innovative development factors in agriculture is related to the need to develop adequate management mechanisms, taking into account the innovative state of the region. A new approach to the innovative development of the agricultural sector will allow to systematically stimulate the innovative development of the regions. New approaches to agriculture, strong scientific research help farms to increase opportunities. The cluster system, which is considered to be a new direction in the agricultural sector in our country, also has innovative solutions. This system has been used in the world in order to improve farms and create the work of skilled staffs in rural areas for many years.

The cluster method(11), activity are focused on achieving general goals and tied to one technologic platform to produce innovative products. Clusters aim to create regional clusters where there is a set of domesticated economic structures. Prospects of innovative development depend on regional and interregional forms of interaction. Effectiveness of clusters is determine by the cost of investments, manufacturing volume, efficiency of diversification of manufacturing based on the cluster's innovative technologies. Introduction of cluster system to the agriculture of our country results in the use of variety of innovations. Not only it improves the modernization of technologies but also also supports digital economy in to agrarian sector. For instance, establishment of cluster system in soya production in South Korea resulted in teaching Korean youth in rural areas preventing them moving in cities to seek jobs. Such cases and issues also exist in our rural areas. If clusters in agrarian sector leads to complete process of crops and conversion of them to finished products they result in introduction of variety of innovative ways and

utilizing them to radically transform the infrastructures in rural areas. Types of agricultural products will increase, their quality and capacity will be enhanced.

Conclusion: The effective use of innovations in the agricultural system of the Republic of Uzbekistan will further expand the potential of the industry, increase the content of products and services, and provide competitive products on the international market. Innovation changes the attitude to work in a positive way. It expands business opportunities in the agricultural sector. This will encourage entrepreneurs to make a profit more. Most importantly, it will provide the population of our country with quality food and expand the range and composition of products. The living standards of the rural population will improve and incomes will increase. In turn, the state should encourage the introduction of innovations in the agricultural sector and form its legal framework at the level of international standards. It is time to support the innovative activities of individuals and legal entities in the agricultural sector.

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